

Educational Escape Room for an Interactive University Class Room

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Abstract—Escape room is a well-known entertainment activity which offers fun and adventure for the participants. And education is the foundation for every successful person and there by the society. But while growing up the learning methods or syllabus are not so interesting while we reach higher grades. Even though we have to understand those important lessons it's a boring procedure to concentrate on something which someone is not so interested. To increase the student engagement in classes and thereby leading to an interactive session escape rooms can be used in a productive way in education. This paper will give an overview of educational escape room and will explain about the four escape rooms developed as a part of this project. These four escape rooms were developed for engineering students and one of them is already used for teaching and this was successful. The results of these will be evaluated further

Index Terms—escape rooms, student engagement, education, game based learning, interactive learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Education outfits individuals with a comprehension of our general surroundings and transforms it into something more noteworthy, alongside making a perspective of taking a gander at life inside us. Additionally, education is a useful asset that gives solidness, monetary security, uniformity, self-reliance, certainty, social acknowledgment, and much more [1]. Obtaining the expressions of the world-popular pioneer Nelson Mandela "Education is the most powerful weapon which you can use to change the world" Therefore, the classroom should be more intuitive, and the strategy for educating should be refreshed for dynamic learning. Educational escape room has started to pick up a foothold in the educational field as of late. Prior study has concentrated on the utilization of numerous sectors of educational escape room [2].

Lately, gamification or game-based learning is a mainstream point and making its situation in the educational area [7],[8]. Proof demonstrates that one of the main components for quality learning is co-operative students and teachers [4]. On 15 July 1982, Don Bennett, a Seattle businessman, turned into the first handicapped man to climb Mount Rainier. On one leg he climbed 14,410 feet, with two supports. It has taken him 5 days. "Bennett said that" You can't do it alone "was the main lesson he gained through his journey [5].

The coordinated effort among students and teachers is a significant factor that prompts the accomplishment of learning. Regardless of whether the educator is exceptionally proficient,

catching student attention for quite a while is something very hard for everybody. Hence, in the new era of education educators anticipate new strategies for teaching to get the maximum yield.

Co-operative learning encourages student accomplishment, makes extra critical connections among students, and in the long run improves student's psychological prosperity. It is both an establishment and a system for some different advances in education including problem-solving, process writing, logical preparation, productive comprehension, and critical reasoning. In addition, this influences the activities and capabilities of educators concerning aggregate work [4]. It is likewise important to realize how to make students more associated with the classroom and encourage engaging learning.

How long are the students focusing on the classes? A few reports show that the normal student's ability to focus on lectures is around 10-15 minutes in length, while most university classes last longer than an hour or more [6]. Furthermore, if the student is doing their hardest to concentrate, factors, for example, outside interruptions and longer sessions negatively affect the student. Students may fall asleep in the early evening classes. This issue must be defeated at any rate to accomplish the best learning experience. At the point when we think about a child, he or she is keen on going to kindergarten or elementary schools. They are keen on playing with their friends alongside that, they learn through games or different classes, however when they grew up classes are getting exhausted as there are not much engaging activities.

Modern teaching methods are significant and are preferred in the technical era. The educational field should utilize new techniques to keep students engaged and alert during the whole session. One of the proposed strategies is utilizing escape room games in a manner to instruct students something while playing. The new educational system utilizes technology and innovations to give the school. The expanding utilization of PC games and applied sciences in learning conditions have impacted both the guidance of teachers and the learning of students.

Game-Based learning can be generally used to improve learning and educating. Perhaps the greatest hindrance for teachers is an achievement in taking huge classes of students, a large number of whom have totally different mentalities, various abilities, and different learning interests. With high

yearnings in anything new, students need a scope of experiences, advantages, astonishment's, and fun to keep up their energy in learning. Looking for creative ways to deal with the interest of students and include them in the learning cycle is likewise one of the key concerns.

Students won't have the option to gain any information and abilities from an exhausting learning measure however will like the utilization of aptitudes and experience to defeat genuine issues with the guide of an effective learning measure. Knowledge and abilities learned by game-based learning are kept up longer than information picked up through other learning methods. An effective learning measure is one in which you are totally keen on what you do. Game-based learning incorporates games that are well developed and have well executed activities to make learning effective. A well planned educational game could mix the learning objectives of the training framework with the enjoyable, completed output of a custom-built game or commercial game. Games explicitly created to train kids have self-learning, and critical thinking and inspiring skills.

Escape Room is a game wherein a group of players cooperates to solve a couple of puzzles or tasks to achieve a specific target in a limited time-frame [3]. The first version of escape room was developed in July 2003 in the USA. Afterward, in 2007, Takao Kato of the Kyoto publisher made a real form of escape game. It has been in Australia since 2011. After about November 2019, over 50,000 escape room have been assessed around the world, which demonstrates an overall acceptance rate [3].

Members in the escape room will have 40-60 minutes to finish the puzzle. Completing each puzzle, they will make a progress to the next puzzle in the game. In the event that they are lost some where, players can request hints. The escape room was a great success with very focused on students and overburdened working experts [9]. Aside from the old kind puzzles utilizing pen and paper, escape rooms are actual locks that can be opened simply subsequent to finding the concealed keys and combinations. These improve the client experience, make more intuitive puzzles, and give the best in general insight.

When escape room has been applied to education as table top escape room, students can open a box after they have solved an entire set of puzzles in an escape room. This is major part of engaging students with studies, and they will have a great time while learning. This can be accomplished in any field of schooling, including geography, health, engineering, science, fitness [10],[11], etc. Since classes are going online because of current conditions, it is essential to get student attention with in classes. Students ought to go to the classes since they are interested to do so, at that point teachers need not be worried over them and the learning and training will be considerably more effective.

Educational escape room is a best topic that can have further development and can be used widely in education for the best output. Hence I decided to do further research on the topic and create some escape room puzzles for engineering students. As

a part of this project first I conducted a literature review on some previous findings related to the topic. Along with that four escape rooms were developed on different engineering topics which includes three puzzles each. The main topics were about cover letter, safety hazards, Hofstede culture (Australian engineering environment), oscilloscope, python and communication engineering. This paper will further explain about the background, design and evaluation of all the four escape room.

II. BACKGROUND/SURVEY

A. Background

Even though I have mentioned about the introduction of Escape room in the introduction, in this section I will further explain about the background of escape room.

Escape rooms were motivated by "escape-the-room"- style computer games. This is likewise the reason of their name.[28] It is also known as Room Escape, Live Escape, Exit Game and Escape Game [27]. Despite the name, escape from a space may not be the fundamental objective for players, nor is the game necessarily limited to a single room .[6]The members in a escape room typically play as a helpful group going somewhere in the range of two and ten players.[28] Players are set up in a number of fictitious environments, such as jail chambers, caves, and space stations. The player's objectives and difficulties they experience typically follow the topic of the room. The game starts with a short prologue to the principles of the game and how to win. This can be conveyed as video, sound, or a game master.[22]

After this, the clock is begun and players have 45 to an hour to finish the game. During this time, players investigate, discover pieces of information, and settle confuses that permit them to advance further in the game. Difficulties in a escape room lean more to mental than physical, and it isn't important to be physically fit to play the game[3].On the off chance that a group stuck somewhere, there is a system set up for the players to request hints. These clues can be conveyed utilizing paper, video, sound, or a game master in the room. If the players can't solve the game's puzzles inside a period limit, the group is normally informed by the game's administrator and accompanied out of the room. The team accomplish the objective inside as far as possible, they win the game.[3] Most escape rooms have signs and codes to open different regions.

Escape room games, which at first started as Flash games for internet browsers and afterward moving onto mobile applications, challenged the participant to find hints and articles while inside a room. The first design to imitate a modern escape room was True Dungeon, premiered at GenCon Indy , in July 2003, in Indianapolis, USA[3].It is situated in Kyoto, Japan and publishes a free magazine by a similar name. Apart from Japan, Captivate Escape Rooms showed up in Australia and Singapore from 2011,[3] the market developing to more than 60 games by 2015.[22]

B. Survey

A literature review has been conducted to find more on this topic and the relevant results are given below.

1) *Gamification In Education To Increase Student Engagement*: Gamification or game-based learning is a very important subject to be addressed today as it is a growing approach for rising student motivation and participation in education [12], [13]. The use of educational games as learning assets is a positive methodology due to their capability to instruct and improve information as well as basic abilities, for example, critical thinking, cooperation, and correspondence. Games have unbelievable inspirational force; they utilize an assortment of methods to propel individuals to draw in with them, some of the time without motivation, just for the fun of playing, and an opportunity to win [14]. These thoughts are like those announced by [15] as they additionally affirm that inspiration and commitment are commonly seen as the requirements for usage and consummation of a task. The purposes behind dropouts or low accomplishment in training incorporate weariness or absence of responsibility, an example of raising absenteeism where every absence makes the individual more averse to re-visitation of school and, in particular, occupied by innovation, for example, cell phones and the web [15].

There are three significant regions where gamification can go about as an intervention which are psychological, passionate, and social. In the intellectual area, games provide the players with convoluted standards frameworks to learn by helpful experimentation and revelation. An illustration of the game Angry Birds is given in which the capacity of the players to beat each other makes them test physicists from a more minor perspective [12]. While in passionate an assortment of extreme feelings is summoned by gamers, from interest to outrage to delight. They have numerous idealistic impressions of feeling, for example, joy and certainty. Essentially, through negative passionate associations, they can help players endure and even transform them into positive ones [12]. The social area urges players to endeavor new jobs and characters and challenge them to settle on in-game choices from their new viewpoints. In games like PUBG players frequently receive less unmistakably non-existent positions, finding new aspects of themselves in the happy with playing space. A bashful young person, for example, could turn into a pack chief, leading many different parts in incredible fights against adversary troops [12]. To put it plainly, if gamification is brought into education it will expand understudy commitment alongside the creation of certain individuals for what's to come. Taken together every one of these examinations are supporting the way that the utilization of gamification or game-based learning in education can expand understudy commitment and lead to a positive learning experience.

2) *Escape Room in Education*: The escape room offers students an opportunity to study and to understand the contents. Instead of a room or a pre-made escape room, lecturers may utilize boxes from educational escape game companies. The escape room provides support and helps learners to learn and

understand the content. The riddles which make up a escape room can be worked around a subject that compares with the class in which it is presented. The possibility of practical gamification isn't to have outer motivators, yet to help players locate a more profound connection to the fundamental topic. Examination demonstrated that the instructive departure room was supported by understudies over customary PC lab meetings. The learning impacts were considered by understudies to be better in the previous. It very well might be contended that adequate utilization of an instructive departure room in programming courses will have major helpful consequences for understudy association and learning. The riddles which are used to set up a escape room can be used to work around a subject that compares the class in which it is presented. The intention of realistic gamification is not to have outer motivators, but to help players to understand the inner meanings of the topic. According to the research conducted escape room is more preferred by students over the computer lab meetings. The learning impacts were considered by students to be better in the previous. It is evident that the efficient utilization of educational escape room in the programming field of education has a significant benefit in learning and student involvement. These outcomes are upheld by another examination where they fabricate a escape room for engineering classes [16]. The Tabletop Escape Room project enables the students to build an escape room on a small scale with complete creative control.[17]

Results show that there are four separate classes of individuals with four separate classes of individuals with whom they chose to interface for different reasons around engineering escape room: researchers, secondary school students, global students[18]. There are wide opportunities to use the escape room decoder for game-related learning, the group says. They see enormous potential for the escape room decoder box to be joined with other equipment like research centre hardware. It is presumed that this as an energizing second for concentrates on gamification, which will add to more certain learning openings [18]. Escape room encloses figure out how to put students close contact with one another, empowering them to cooperate in an actual climate. Organizing the game by carefully unfurling the riddles and pre-set hints decreased the instructor's requirement for help. Students will be tested and inundated in conditions in reality, for instance, socio-logical issues including plastic soup. A combination of pre-set pieces of information and instructors with a part in the story merits researching in a future report. As indicated by the specialists, the outside of escape boxes might be altered, and the material of boxes reused to make them more suitable for study hall use [19].

3) *Recreational vs Educational escape room*: Apart from the recreational escape room in the field of entertainment, educational escape room are fabricated mainly as learning conditions. A negligible prerequisite for the use in education is that riddles should be coordinated with the educational plan and to meet the ideal learning results, students need their subject aptitudes and capacities. In a departure game,

however, players focus on finishing the objective of the game inside as far as possible, and less on finishing instructive targets or not. Thus, the plan needs to guarantee that students meet the instructive targets accomplished by accomplishing the game objective. [20] alludes to arrangement as a positive arrangement in zones of training framework. A subsequent basis for making an instructional escape room is similarity with learning goals and riddles [19].

The possibility of the escape room requires a common reason, alongside a longing for cooperation to beat issues and satisfy that point as expected. Moral constructionists in training elevate students to create mindfulness in contact with each other. The educators present escape room focused on social constructive to advance group arranged or group learning [21]. The subsequent plan models for an instructive escape room is dynamic commitment inside groups [19]. While considering the group association groups as a rule play in a steady progression in the recreational escape room [22]. Instructors will in general seek all players simultaneously in one class room in instructive conditions, rather than one group after another, as it diminishes the hour of the mentor and the inhabitants of a study hall [21]. A climate in the classroom confines organizing and hardware and takes out inundation with regards to the game. The feeling of the game is significant since it interfaces puzzles in an important way. Learning is focused at concentrating to a bigger setting than the classroom. A game sense can challenge students with issues of the rest of the world or socio-logical inquiries [19].

Game bosses video track and lead groups from the neighbouring room in the recreational escape room. Notwithstanding, in instructive escape room instructors will in general lead groups, as opposed to from an adjoining space, in a similar space. Video reconnaissance restrains their perception and translation of social elements and the scholarly development of students [19]. Additionally, in instructive escape room financial plans are typically restricted. Thus, educators have restricted time and financial plan to create showing materials and henceforth they energize reusable and multi-functional instructing and learning materials [21]. So, planning inexhaustible items will be functioning admirably here.

Escape room	Recreational	Educational
Goals	Primarily on entertainment	Primarily on learning
Pedagogy	Players collaborate	Learners work & learn collaboratively
Team organization	Teams play one after another	Learners work in the same room at the same time
Location	One or more connected permanent rooms	Classroom with time slots
Materials	Preparation time & budget varies	Restricted preparation time & limited budget
Staging	Fixed scenery, props, sound and smell	Classroom setting
Guiding	From an adjacent room	Within the same room

Fig. 1. Fig 1:Recreational vs Educational Escape room

4) *Framework for Developing A Good Escape Room:* The system for building up a decent escape room for educational purposes is clarified in both [15] and [23]. Despite the fact

that they share some normal thoughts there are a few contrasts too. Considering [15] there are 5 stages in the design cycle of an escape room. A flow chart is given in Fig.1. The initial step is understanding the intended audience and the context. An objective segment exploration can help survey factors, for example, age gathering, social experience, existing skillset, and so forth. It would help in building up an educational program following the setting in which the item is being given. For instance, students may miss concentration because of yearning if the learning program is kept just before lunch [15]. In the second the learning goals should be characterized. The educator can have a target that he/she needs the student to meet toward the finish of the learning educational program. This may incorporate general instructive targets, for example, the student finishing an assignment, a test, a quiz, or an exam, a venture. Explicit learning targets may incorporate perceiving an idea by the student, having the option to finish an errand during the preparation, or completing the learning program. Behavioural objectives are which can empower the students to focus on class [15].

Fig. 2. Fig 2:Steps in framework

Structuring the experience of the student is the third step. Steps and targets are significant instruments that urge instructors to plan data and measure what the students need to comprehend and achieve before the end of-stage or cycle. Stage 4 is to recognize the resources required for the escape room. While examining gamification, an educator ought to consider questions including: Can a tracking technique be stretched out to this specific stage? What will the money be and what will conclude this present stage’s accomplishment? Will there be a coordinated technique to give a contribution to the student or potentially the educator? The last step is to apply the gamification components that are self-components and social components [15].

In the research and experiments used in [23], there are 6 stages in the escape room structure. The steps are given in Fig 2. The initial step of the two journals [15],[23] share the very thought that is understanding the participants. In specific zones, a review of the intended interest group is considered as an ordinary methodology. It’s basic for electronic game firms to gather information on their user base. Toward the start of building up their educational escape room, the Participants stage is separated into five areas for engineers to assess. The five areas are User type, time, difficulty, mode, scale, length of experience, and the number of participants. In the second stage additionally, they [15],[23] share similar thoughts of goals. Creating targets right off the bat in the planning process for the game interface will imply that the interface is built deliberately.

To additional shape the learning plan or results, these objectives can be worked into the style, its riddles, and its

chosen mode. Defining unmistakable objectives empowers the production of an examination intends to gauge players' learning performance, learning accomplishment. The third step is choosing the theme. Because of the short contact time frame that the players need to play in the games, the escape room has clear themes and storylines. The theme stage is partitioned into four territories to be explored by engineers in their plan cycle [23]. The fourth stage system is for engineers to consider planning the puzzles and occasions in which the players can draw in all through the game. Puzzles should be adjusted to the information set up about different strides of the system. The fifth phase of the system cycle is to recognize any area or hardware that designers are probably going to use to upgrade their game insight. The 6th and last stage in the framework are for designers to see how the game experience can be measured. This stage is utilized to prompt the data collection process and to decide the general adequacy and impact of data sharing on the projects. Utilizing the information acquired from the assessment to prompt any additionally required improvement is helpful [23].

5) Methods Used in The Educational Escape Room :

The primary concept is a tabletop escape room in which the escape room experience is contained in a little box [17]. The games energize a group of players to solve from the solace of their home a series of issues. They used this item to a first-year engineering student venture by synchronizing the puzzle specifications with the learning objectives. As students have contending innovative ideas, the escape room made by the small groups differed enormously. Figure 3 displays two separate plans for the Tabletop Escape Room. And the project has similar specifications, achievements, and rubrics however the outcomes are fundamentally extraordinary [17]. Another idea is to build up a traditional escape room. Using software like AutoCAD, 3D printing, and laser cutting the prototypes are made physically. It is shown in Fig 4. A comparable thought of making an escape box is mentioned in [19].

Fig. 3. Fig 3:Table top escape room

Fig. 4. Fig 4:Traditional Escape Room

Using computer-based escape room puzzles is a high level strategy that can be used to teach programming segments for students. In this technique, a computer-based, and physical puzzles are consolidated, and students should unravel them in a restricted measure of time [16]. In the wake of completing the first set of puzzles, students can proceed to the following

set. The intriguing piece of the computer-based escape room is the narration. As appeared in Fig 5 toward the start of the puzzle there will be a narration about the situation which will be a real-time experience that can build student commitment [16].

Fig. 5. Fig 5:Narration in computer-based escape room

The decoder box [24] is broadly suggested for an educational escape room and is endorsed by participants. Unlike the methods above, this decoder box handles the entirety of the difficulties of making a completely vivid, active, and flexible research platform that has consolidated data processing. Decoder box has a built-in battery with over 20 hours of life, additionally coming with USB charging. Three numerical codes can be conceivable, so 3 distinct puzzles can be made every one of 18-digit lengths. Data analytics available which can store wrong conjectures and time taken per round. The vital part of the decoder box is an Arduino Nano which is a convenient low-cost platform and simple to change or fix. There is a 2-line LCD board that shows the clock, the response code, and the number of digits in the answer code. To associate with the decoder, the players use a mathematical keypad, which gives the numbers 0-9 [24],[25]. Fig 6 shows the picture of a decoder box.

Fig. 6. Fig 6: The decoder box

The next idea is the Web Interface, which is a Java Script interface that recreates the functionality of the electronic decoder box. There are a number of recently accessible online escape rooms on Google, we are using one with added functionalities including timer, clues distribution, and data analytic. Each solution is stored as an MD5 hash – preventing students from trying to cheat on any solutions as plain text[26].

6) *Limitations and Challenges:* Studies [21] affirmed at least one advantage, however, more were recorded by the larger part. The escape room has been found to support communication and participation. Students enrolled benefit in learning and improved excitement, as they discover more pleasant learning by play. The involvement with the escape room reinforced and fortified social connections, which helped

to develop a feeling of belonging. An escape room can be repeated for different classes ordinarily and have a backup tool for content examination. They can likewise be used to create critical thinking capabilities and to tackle issues [21].

When using the escape room in educational conditions, a portion of the chosen studies distinguished a couple of challenges. The poor evaluation applies to the most recorded trouble. Small sample sizes and limited frameworks, for example, space or facilitator accessibility, are other recorded deterrents. Large group sizes created practical issues, as it was inconceivable for instructors to execute the training in various periods or for members to take an interest in the activities in detail. While it may be inexpensive to build an educational escape room, budget restrictions are additionally stated [21].

III. DESIGN/METHODOLOGY

The primary aim of the project was to create 4 escape room's for educational purposes. After detailed research a literature review was developed which contain the already available data about escape room and gamification in education. Along with this we started working on developing escape room on 4 different topics for engineering students. The detailed designing of each puzzles for all the 4 escape room's will be described in this section.

A. Design

1) *Escape Room 1:* Escape room 1 was created for the semester 1 EMS5AEE students at La Trobe University. The main idea of this escape room was to teach some main concepts of Australian Engineering Environment which includes writing a cover letter, Hofstede cultural dimensions, and safety in workplace. Instead of taking a long lecture on this we created some puzzles, by solving these puzzles students learn about the topics better. At the beginning of puzzle a scenario is made to make the game more interesting. For this escape room the scenario is as; the students are the candidates for an interview. And they failed for the specific interview, meanwhile the HR manager asked them to solve some specific tasks so that they can get a chance to work in a specific team of that firm. This introduction leads the students to the puzzles

The first puzzle is finding errors in a cover letter. For doing this we made a cover letter which includes 6 common errors in cover letters. Each line of the cover letter is sequentially numbered. When student find an error from the cover letter the number corresponding to that line will be the first digit of the key. When the student finds all the 6 errors and arrange them in the ascending order of the lines of the cover letter they will get an 8 digit key as the answer. If they missed any of them, the answer may go wrong. If the student got stuck somewhere one digit of the answer will be displayed in the decoder every 5 minutes. The example cover letter is given in Figure 7. After finishing puzzle 1 students can move on to puzzle 2.

The second puzzle is about safety in workplace. For this we have selected some safety hazards including tripping, slipping, falling etc. Images of each hazards will be given, and each

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2nd April 2020
Dear Sir,
I am writing to apply for the position of graduate electronics engineer being offered by ABC Systems. Previously I was working at Technical Corporation Solutions, but I recently resigned because of a poor manager and inadequate pay.
I am extremely excited at the prospect of working for Carmichael Industries as you are one of the one the largest defence contractors in Australia. I'm particularly interested in your aerospace research division. I have over 2 years' experience in supermarket merchandising and was twice rated employee of the month.
While doing my undergraduate degree in Electronics and Communication Engineering I have involved in many projects including design integration and implementation of diodes and advanced radar physics. I achieved an average mark of 85% which shows my dedication and mastery around my studies.
Along with my resume I have included a reference from my professors and the supervisor of

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Fig. 7. Fig 7: Cover Letter

image are divided in to 7-8 portions. This is given in Figure 8. Students must find out which portion of the image contain hazard and the number given for that portion will a digit of the answer key.

Fig. 8. Fig 8: Safety Hazard

The third puzzle is about Hofstede cultural dimensions. In this we have selected 7 countries which are Australia, Japan, Canada, India, Brazil, Switzerland and United States. And graphs which contain the 5 cultural dimensions of each country is given. This given in the form of a graph. Four questions from the lecture notes are asked and students need to find which are those 2 countries with the most difference in that culture. The answer will be difference of the highest and lowest country. So, there will be 2 digits from each question giving an 8-digit key as the answer. Few graphs are given in Figure 3.

Fig. 9. Fig 9: Hofstede cultural dimensions

2) *Escape Room 2:* The escape room 2 was designed to teach about the characteristics of electronic wave forms. The scenario for this puzzle was the student got a flyer of a concert while walking through a street. This concert offer a free ticket (which cost 50 dollars) for one who win a game. The game is solve the puzzles which include the musical signals of the concert. To create the wave forms an online platform named virtual oscilloscope was used.

The first puzzle is to find the frequency of the given wave forms after observing the graphs carefully. Four wave forms

were given and a table for frequency was also given. Students has to find the frequency of the given signals and convert the answer in to the answer key using the given table of frequency and hints. A screenshot of that is given in Figure 4

Fig. 10. Fig 10: Wave form

The second puzzle was to find the peak to peak voltage of the given graphs. This was a quite simple one. Students have to round figure the answer and form it to the answer key.

The third puzzle was to find the duty cycle of the given wave forms. There were 3 wave forms given and the answer was in six digits. Students can use the duty cycle directly to get the answer key.

3) *Escape Room 3:* The third escape room was also for engineering students made to teach python. the three puzzles covered different areas of python programming.

In the first puzzle different python programs were given to students which contain some errors, student need to find those errors. Each line of the program is numbered such that the answer key is the line number which has the error.

In the second puzzle students were supposed to find the output of the given python programs. Some small python programs were given and students has to find the output of the given program. The output of each program is the direct digit for the answer key. The answer was an 8 digit key.

The last puzzle was some programs to teach the string operators. Some programs using different string operators were given and some possible output options were given. Students have to select the correct output of the program from the given options.

4) *Escape Room 4:* Escape room 4 was designed to teach some concepts of communication engineering. The scenario was explained as the participant is working for Australian Defence force and they got some unauthorised signals. They have to work on these signals to solve the puzzles.

The puzzle 1 was about Manchester Encoding . Five signals are given which are encoded using Manchester encoding. Students are supposed to find out the error in the signals. The answer is a 5 digit code.

The second puzzle was about different types of parity checks. It contain questions with a variety of parity checks and students will learn about adding and checking parity bits.

The third puzzle was about Longitudinal redundancy check. Students has find the parity code for the data transmission

B. Methodology

1) *Research Approach:* There are a few methodologies accessible for each exploration and each analyst can utilize their

own chosen approach for their examination as indicated by the subject. For each examination theme, the principal thought is to locate the primary and secondary information on the point. secondary information is the information effectively accessible on the web while primary information is the information each specialist needs to discover without help from anyone else or herself. For some exploration points, secondary information may sufficiently be to complete the examination. Also, for my point there was a great deal of secondary information accessible and I utilized without a doubt, not much primary information.

The following class of approach is a quantitative methodology and qualitative methodology. The assortment and investigation strategy for mathematical information is quantitative methodology. It very well may be utilized to distinguish connections and midpoints, to make expectations, to test connections, and to sum up results to bigger populations. To explain ideas, conclusions, or perceptions, subjective examination requires assembling and evaluating non-mathematical information. It could be utilized to gather top to bottom data into a point or grow new examination thoughts. For my subject I generally need quantitative techniques which incorporate reviews. Another class, that is exploratory, or re-enactment approach is likewise utilized in examination. In any case, for my subject it isn't vital. Details of the research approaches will be given in this report.

2) *Research Design:* Research on the point 'Educational escape room for understudies' was done as a component of the course prerequisite of my post-graduation. This theme was intriguing and can be utilized carefully to roll out great improvements in instructive area along these lines making a superior method of learning. As innovative progression is fast now daily's new strategies should be actualized in instructing to give superior quality training to new age. We were intending to make 3-4 escape room for designing understudies during the exploration. The exploration is done in a 5-month time span from July 2020 to December 2020. Four escape rooms were finished during this time. The information necessity for each exploration fluctuates likewise. Prior to doing the riddles and exploration on the riddle themes, a divine being research on the escape room was required. For the escape room there was a ton of secondary information accessible. secondary information is the information effectively accessible in distributions, web, diaries, papers, magazines and so forth. It is most effortless strategy for information assortment. For the escape rooms we made, despite the fact that optional information was accessible some essential information was likewise required.

Essential information is a classification of information that analysts acquire straightforwardly from essential sources through meetings, reviews, contemplates, and so on Essential information sources are ordinarily chosen and adjusted correctly to suit the measures or details of a specific report. Prior to choosing a hotspot for information assortment, things, for example, the purpose of the investigation and the intended interest group should likewise be recognized. A writing survey was directed subsequent to gather the primary information. A

subjective technique for information assortment will be viable for my examination as I need subjective information, sentiments, perceptions and so forth the techniques for information assortment and the investigation of the information will be clarified underneath.

3) *Research Method:* The data collection tool chosen for my study is a qualitative method and experiments have been done to find more secondary data. The methods of data collection for each escape room will be explained below. At first, I focused on researching the escape room. The following subjects were extensively analysed, and a systematic analysis was undertaken. Gamification in education to increase student engagement, Escape room in education, Recreational vs educational escape room, the framework for developing a good escape room, Methods used in the educational escape room, Limitations and challenges of escape room education, etc are the main topics discussed.

Secondary study was performed as there was a wide abundance of data on these subjects. Almost all scholars are promoting the implementation of gamification in schooling. Although different writers choose different approaches to introduce escape rooms in schools. The performance of each escape room is the design process, and steps should be taken to produce the best outcomes. Even though the escape room is one of the best methods for the learning process, they also have some limitations.

IV. RESULTS, DISCUSSION EVALUATION

To analyse the effectiveness of the escape room we have obtained a survey for the first escape room. The first escape room was used for the EMS5AEE students and after doing the escape room an online survey was provided. The questions given for the online survey were:

1. How many in-person escape rooms have you done previously?
2. How many educational escape rooms have you done previously (like this one)?
3. For puzzle rank the level of difficulty as you perceived it:
4. For puzzle rank how much you enjoyed it:
5. How much do you think you learnt in each of the following puzzles?
6. Please select the most appropriate response:
7. Any other comments?

All the survey results will be attached in the Appendix as it is not intact to do here.

For the first question, about 70 percent of the students have done 3-4 escape rooms before and for a 14 percent it was their first experience. The second question was about educational escape rooms and about 20-30 percent haven't done educational escape rooms before.

The third question was about the difficulty level of the puzzles. The puzzle about safety was easy or medium for the majority. Cover letter was also similar. For Hofstede the majority felt it was medium or hard.

The fourth question was about the enjoyment in which nobody disliked it. All the students either liked or strongly liked all the 3 puzzles. This indicates that students were really happy with these escape room. The fifth question was about what they learned from the escape rooms. More than 80 percent of the students have learned something from all the three puzzles. This indicates that our escape room was a success for teaching.

The last question has a lot of options and it is given below as figure 11. From that we can see that all the students are satisfied by the escape room activity. Also in the comment box students have requested for more escape room activities because they are super fun.

Please select the most appropriate response:

	STRONGLY DISAGREE	DISAGREE	UNSURE	AGREE	STRONGLY AGREE	TOTAL	WEIGHTED AVERAGE
I learned to complete the escape room activity	0	0	0	7	35	42	4.50
I found the activity difficult	21	43	0	0	28	71	2.87
I felt that the escape room activity	0	0	0	7	35	42	4.50
I enjoyed the escape room activity	0	0	0	21	43	64	4.79
I felt satisfied in the escape room activity	0	0	0	7	42	49	4.43
I liked the business aspect of the escape room activity	0	0	0	1	42	43	4.43
I became unaware of the surrounding a while during the escape room activity	21	21	0	14	14	50	3.87
I felt disappointed in the escape room activity	7	14	0	0	50	57	3.93
I found the escape room activity interesting	0	0	0	0	57	42	4.43
I did not participate in the escape room activity	50	21	0	0	21	71	2.14

Fig. 11. Fig 11: Survey question 6

Hence it can be concluded that the escape room activity was really interesting and students have learnt the topics during the activity. As the students are requesting for more escape room activities this should be further developed and used in all sectors of education. Among the eight teams, six teams were able to finish the escape room in the given time.

V. CONCLUSION

Failure to interactive learning was a major problem equally faced by teachers and students. Even if the students try to concentrate they can't do it for a long time. And even though the best teacher is taking classes it is difficult for him to teach if the whole class is not responding. This is not the mistake of either the teacher or the student. This problem should be solved and classes should be more interactive which increases the student engagement. To solve this issue we had put forward the idea of educational escape room.

Escape rooms were introduced into education as a part of game based learning. Educational escape rooms can be used in any sector including history, geography, biology, health or engineering. As a part of this project we have created 4 escape rooms for engineering students.

The four escape rooms were based on Australian engineering environment, waveform characteristics, python programming and communication engineering. All the four escape rooms were successfully developed and the first escape room was used for teaching students. After doing the escape rooms

a online survey was conducted and the results showed that students really enjoyed the escape rooms along with learning. This was our primary objective and we were really happy for this result. Gamification in learning is a revolutionary idea that can change the existing educational system in to a better one and educational escape room is one of the best choice to introduce this idea in to class rooms.

Only four escape rooms were created during this time but this can be further developed. As my major is on electronics and communication the escape rooms were created related to this topic. But the results indicate that every student will love this and this should be introduced in to different categories. Not only in universities this can be used for education in schools as well. I highly encourage teachers to try this atleast once in their classes and definitely they will use that afterwards.

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VIII. APPENDIX

How many in-person escape rooms have you done previously?

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
0	14.29%
1	7.14%
2	7.14%
3	21.43%
4+	50.00%
TOTAL	14

Fig. 12. Fig 12: Survey Question 1

How many educational escape rooms have you done previously (like this one)?

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
0	21.43%
1	7.14%
2	14.29%
3	42.86%
4+	14.29%
TOTAL	14

Fig. 13. Fig 13: Survey Question 2

For puzzle rank how much you enjoyed it:

	STRONGLY DISLIKED	DISLIKED	UNSURE	LIKED	STRONGLY LIKED	TOTAL	WEIGHTED AVERAGE
Puzzle 1 (Cover Letter)	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	14	4.50
Puzzle 2 (Safety)	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	42.86%	57.14%	8	4.57
Puzzle 3 (Hotwade)	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	7	4.50

Fig. 14. Fig 14: Survey Question 3

For puzzle rank how much you enjoyed it:

	STRONGLY DISLIKED	DISLIKED	UNSURE	LIKED	STRONGLY LIKED	TOTAL	WEIGHTED AVERAGE
Puzzle 1 (Cover Letter)	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	14	4.50
Puzzle 2 (Safety)	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	42.86%	57.14%	8	4.57
Puzzle 3 (Hotwade)	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	7	4.50

Fig. 15. Fig 15: Survey Question 4

How much do you think you learnt in each of the following puzzles?

	VERY LITTLE	A LITTLE	UNSURE	QUITE A BIT	A LOT	TOTAL	WEIGHTED AVERAGE
Puzzle 1 (Cover Letter)	0.00%	7.14%	0.00%	35.71%	57.14%	14	4.43
Puzzle 2 (Safety)	0.00%	7.14%	7.14%	35.71%	50.00%	8	4.29
Puzzle 3 (Hotwade)	0.00%	0.00%	14.29%	21.43%	64.29%	7	4.50

Fig. 16. Fig 16: Survey Question 5